

Proof of Theorem 3

- intuition behind its simplification-

This short document provides the intuition behind the simplification of the proof of Theorem 3 (presented in the paper titled “As easy as ABC: Optimal (A)ccountable (B)yzantine (C)onsensus is easy!”). Theorem 3 states that any accountable Byzantine consensus algorithm has an execution e such that (1) correct processes disagree in e , and (2) correct processes send cubic number of authenticators¹ in e .

Intuition. We consider an accountable Byzantine consensus protocol Π^A executed among n processes, where $n = 3t_0 + 1$. If up to t_0 processes are faulty, Π^A solves Byzantine consensus; if correct processes disagree, Π^A ensures that every correct process obtains a proof of culpability of $t_0 + 1$ processes.

Step 1: In order to build the execution e , we separate processes into three disjoint groups:

1. group A with t_0 processes; each process $a \in A$ is correct and proposes 0,
2. group B with $t_0 + 1$ processes; each process $b \in B$ is faulty,
3. group C with t_0 processes; each process $c \in C$ is correct and proposes 1.

Next, we delay all messages exchanged between processes from groups A and C . Moreover, all processes from B behave towards processes from A as if they are correct and they proposed 0 and all processes from B behave towards processes from C as if they are correct and they proposed 1. Therefore, all processes from group A decide 0 and all processes from group C decide 1. The overview of the first step is given in Figure 1.

Importantly, the only way for any process $b \in B$ to be detected is for processes from groups A and C to communicate because processes from group B behaved correctly towards all processes from group A (resp., C). Therefore, processes from groups A and C must communicate in order to ensure accountability.

Step 2: All processes from group A become Byzantine, except for a single process that remains correct. On the other hand, all processes from group C remain correct. Finally, all processes from group B decide to become silent forever. The execution overview at this point is illustrated in Figure 2.

Step 3: Finally, we delay all messages between the single correct process from group A (the “last” one from Figure 2) and all processes from group C . Moreover, we delay all messages between processes from group C . Hence, after the second step of creating

¹An authenticator is either a partial signagure or a signature.

Figure 1: Step 1 of creating e .

Figure 2: Step 2 of creating e .

e , (1) correct processes from group C communicate only with faulty processes from group A , and (2) messages between the correct process from group A and correct processes from group C are delayed.

In order to conclude final step of creating e , we present the communication pattern between a faulty process from group A and a correct process from group C (see Figure 3). Namely, each faulty process $a \in A$ acts towards a correct process $c \in C$ as if a has decided 0 and has not heard from any other process after the decision. Process a looks correct to process c and process c concludes that the current execution might be the one in which only processes a and c are correct; hence, c must collaborate with a to ensure that a obtains a proof of culpability of $t_0 + 1$ processes. In order to do so, process c needs to send at least $t_0 + 1 = \Omega(n)$ authenticators.

Finally, all $t_0 - 1$ faulty processes from group A can apply this tactics and process $c \in C$ must help each one of those processes. Therefore, c sends $(t_0 - 1)(t_0 + 1)$

authenticators, which is quadratic number of authenticators. Since all $t_0 - 1$ faulty processes from group A can apply this tactics towards *all* processes from group C (since messages between processes from group C are delayed), all processes from group C send quadratic number of authenticators. Thus, there are $(t_0 + 1)^2(t_0 - 1)$ authenticators sent by correct processes in e , which implies the cubic overall bit complexity.

Figure 3: Step 3 of creating e .